

Popular Article

Hypoglycaemia of baby pigs

Dr. A. Jayasri¹, Dr. G. Ugander Reddy², Dr. B. Sampath Kumar³

¹Assistant Professor & Head, Dept. of Veterinary Biochemistry, C. V. Sc., Rajendranagar, PVNRTVU.

²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Veterinary Biochemistry, C. V. Sc., Rajendranagar, PVNRTVU.

³Assistant Professor, Dept. of Veterinary Biochemistry, C. V. Sc., Mamnoon, PVNRTVU.

Hypoglycemia is a condition associated with fall in blood sugar level and is the most common cause of death in piglets causing heavy losses among piglets under first week of age due to 15 to 25 % mortality. During the first few days of life, the new born piglet is unable to mobilize the low glycogen reserves in the liver to provide adequate levels of glucose in the blood. So, it depends on regular intake of lactose from the sow's milk. If a piglet cannot obtain sufficient lactose to maintain its energy output, it runs out of energy, its body temperature drops and ultimately it goes in to a coma state and dies.

Etiology

- Inadequate intake of milk by piglets
- Large litter size with inadequate number of teats
- Presence of mastitis, milk fever, nipple necrosis and farrowing hysteria
- Presence of hemolytic diseases, buccal lesions and anaphylactic shock
- Secondary to diseases like coliform septicemia, streptococcal infections, myoclonia, acute diarrhea and transmissible gastro enteritis
- Cold and wet environment
- Administration of insulin in larger doses

Pathogenesis

At birth, piglets normally possess carbohydrate reserves in the form of hepatic glycogen stores (10-14 mg/100 g) and blood glucose levels greater than 110 mg/dl. Glycogen reserves soon get depleted if the milk supply is inadequate. Feeding normally provide adequate blood glucose levels but if interrupted, its blood glucose drops rapidly to hypoglycemic levels (< 40 mg/dl) within 24-36 hours. Gluconeogenic mechanisms are underdeveloped at birth in piglets due to inactive gluconeogenic enzymes which get induced by feeding and they reach their maximal activities within 1-2 weeks after birth. In addition to it, low environmental temperatures lead to increased utilization of glycogen reserves in the liver and to the more rapid development of clinical signs.

Clinical findings

- Symptoms appear within 48 hrs of birth
- Involvement of piglets in a litter at the same time
- Marked behavioural change from normal suckling and playing in to a sleepy and lethargic attitude
- Piglets appear dull, shiver, wander aimlessly and have a rough coat
- Subnormal temperature, cold clammy pale colour skin and lateral or sternal recumbency
- In later stages, Breathlessness, nervousness, excitement and convulsions with champing of jaws, Salivation contraction of limbs, opisthotonus, nystagmus, coma and death occur within 24 – 36 hrs.

Necropsy findings

- Presence of minimal ingesta in the alimentary tract
- Dehydration
- Small hard liver
- Frequently a white precipitate in renal pelvis

Diagnosis

- Based on age, symptoms, necropsy findings and fall in blood glucose level to 30-40mg/dl in affected piglets
- Elevation of Blood urea nitrogen

Treatment and control

- Administration of colostrum @ 15 to 30 ml/kg body wt within a few minutes after birth in to stomach using catheter or syringe
- Piglets with primary hypoglycemia should be given 15 ml of 25% glucose solution intraperitoneally and repeated 4-6 hr until they suck milk
- Administration of I/V glucose in severe cases
- Treated pigs should be placed in warm environment
- New born piglets should be protected from cold by maintaining the environmental temperature between 90-95°F.
- Intra gastric administration of 30-50 ml of 5% dextrose or evaporated milk diluted with half volume water.
- Distribution of uneven litters.

Conclusion

By taking appropriate measures like feeding the piglets immediately after birth and maintaining warm environmental temperature can significantly reduce the mortality rate which is of a great economic importance for pig farming

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